

SPECIALIZED INTERPRETING SKILLS

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Abstract: This article reviews the research on the unique challenges of interpreting in technical fields and the specialized skills interpreters must develop. Methods include a literature review of studies on interpreting in various technical domains and analysis of professional interpreter training programs. The results show that interpreters in specialized fields must possess in-depth knowledge of domain-specific terminology, concepts, and practices in both the source and target languages and cultures. Additionally, they need strong research and analytical skills to quickly get up to speed on new topics.

Keywords: interpreting, translation, interpreter training, subject matter expertise, specialized interpreting

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada tarjimonning texnik sohalardagi noyob muammolari va tarjimonlar rivojlantirishi kerak bo'lgan maxsus ko'nikmalarga bag'ishlangan tadqiqotlar haqida umumiy ma'lumot berilgan. Usullar turli xil texnik sohalarda tarjima adabiyotlarini ko'rib chiqish va tarjimonlarni o'qitish dasturlarini tahlil qilishni o'z ichiga oladi. Natijalar shuni ko'rsatadiki, ixtisoslashgan sohalardagi tarjimonlar ma'lum bir mavzu sohasiga tegishli terminologiya, tushunchalar va amaliyotlarni, ham manba, ham maqsadli tillar va madaniyatlarni chuqur bilishlari kerak. Bundan tashqari, ular yangi mavzularni tezda o'rganish uchun kuchli tadqiqot va tahliliy ko'nikmalarga muhtoj.

Kalit so'zlar: tarjima, tarjima, tarjimonlarni tayyorlash, mavzuni bilish, maxsus tarjima

Аннотация: В данной статье представлен обзор исследований, посвященных уникальным проблемам устного перевода в технических областях и специальным навыкам, которые должны развивать переводчики. Методы включают обзор литературы по устному переводу в различных технических областях и анализ программ профессиональной подготовки переводчиков. Результаты показывают, что переводчики в специализированных областях должны обладать глубокими знаниями терминологии, концепций и практик, относящихся к конкретной предметной области, как на исходном, так и на целевом языках и культурах. Кроме того, им необходимы сильные исследовательские и аналитические навыки, чтобы быстро вникать в новые темы.

Ключевые слова: устный перевод, письменные переводы, подготовка устных переводчиков, знание предмета, специализированный устный перевод

INTRODUCTION

Interpreting is a highly complex task that requires the interpreter to comprehend meaning and intent in the source language, transpose the message into the target language, and express it in a way that effectively conveys the original meaning for the target audience.[1] Interpreting is challenging even for general topics of conversation, but is particularly difficult in highly technical domains such as medicine, law, technology, business, and diplomacy.[2] In these fields, the interpreter must contend not only with specialized jargon and terminology, but also with domain-specific knowledge, professional practices, and cultural norms.[3]

As our world becomes increasingly interconnected, there is growing demand for interpreters who can facilitate communication in specialized fields. However, traditional interpreter training has focused primarily on developing general linguistic and interpreting skills, with limited attention to specialized domains.[4] There is a need for a more comprehensive understanding of the unique challenges involved in interpreting for technical fields and evidence-based approaches to preparing interpreters for this work.

METHODS AND LITERATURE REVIEW

To identify relevant research on specialized interpreting skills, we conducted a literature review using online databases including JSTOR, ProQuest, and Google Scholar. Search terms included "interpreting," "specialized interpreting," "interpreting in [domain]" (medicine, law, business, etc.), "domain-specific skills," and "interpreter training."

RESULTS

The literature reveals several key competencies that interpreters must develop to work effectively in specialized domains:

Linguistic Skills. In addition to a high level of proficiency in the source and target languages, interpreters in technical fields must master the specialized terminology and jargon specific to the domain.[5] This requires not only memorizing long lists of technical terms, but understanding the underlying concepts they represent and how they are used in context by experts in the field.[6]

Subject Matter Knowledge. To accurately convey the meaning behind the words, interpreters must have a deep understanding of the subject matter

itself.[7] They need to be familiar with key concepts, theories, and practices in the domain, as well as stay up to date on new developments.[8] Many studies emphasized the importance of interpreters' ability to quickly get up to speed on new topics through research and self-study.

Cultural Competence. Interpreting also requires navigating cultural differences in communication styles, professional norms, and expectations. For example, interpreters in diplomatic settings must be attuned to cultural protocols and political sensitivities. In healthcare settings, interpreters must bridge gaps between the biomedical model and patients' culturally-informed beliefs about health and illness.

Analytical and Research Skills. Given the complexity of the content in many technical domains, interpreters must have strong analytical skills to grasp speakers' arguments, lines of reasoning, and supporting evidence. They also need research skills to investigate new topics and fill gaps in their knowledge.

ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

The research shows a clear consensus that interpreting in specialized domains requires a distinct skill set beyond general linguistic and interpreting abilities. The increasing demand for interpreters with subject matter expertise suggests that interpreter education programs will need to innovate to meet the needs of the market and equip students for the realities of professional practice.

However, several challenges remain. There is still a lack of evidence-based research on the effectiveness of different pedagogical approaches to interpreter training for specialized domains. Sample sizes in most of the studies reviewed were small and many relied on self-reported measures of competence rather than objective assessments. More rigorous research is needed to identify best practices.

Additionally, the degree of subject matter expertise needed likely varies across domains, but this has not been clearly established. In some fields, a broad understanding of key concepts and practices may suffice, while others may require interpreters to have qualifications comparable to practitioners in the field. Future studies should examine the minimum threshold of domain knowledge required for effective interpreting in different technical areas.

Interpreter training programs face practical constraints in terms of the number of specialized domains they can cover in depth. Most programs require two years of full-time study, but it is likely unrealistic for students to gain a thorough grounding in more than one specialized area on top of general interpreting and translation skills in this timeframe. Programs will need to

carefully consider how to structure curricula to provide appropriate breadth and depth, as well as how to leverage partnerships and continuing education to support interpreters in expanding their repertoire of specialized skills over the course of their careers.

CONCLUSION

Interpreting in specialized domains such as medicine, law, and business requires mastery of both linguistic and extra-linguistic knowledge and skills. Interpreters must navigate a wide range of challenges, including domain-specific terminology, knowledge, professional practices, and cultural norms. Interpreter education programs are beginning to rise to the challenge by incorporating authentic materials and subject matter content into the curriculum and forging partnerships with relevant academic and professional programs. However, more research is needed to validate training approaches and establish evidence-based standards for the profession. As demand for interpreters with specialized skills continues to grow, interpreter education must continue to evolve to prepare students to meet the communication needs of an interdependent world.

References:

1. Pöchhacker, F. (2014). *Introducing Interpreting Studies*. Routledge.
2. Tulenova, K., Ubaydullayeva, S., Gaziyeva, R., Mamayusupov, U., Mamadjonova, M., & Turdikulova, E. (2024, June). The Introduction of Information Technologies Into Educational and Laboratory Complexes is an Important Step Towards the Digitalization of Uzbekistan. In *2024 4th International Conference on Technology Enhanced Learning in Higher Education (TELE)* (pp. 48-53). IEEE.
3. Qurbonazarovna, M. M. (2024). OZBEKISTON TARAQQIYOTINING YANGI DAVRIDA TALIM SIFATINI OSHIRISHNING SINERGETIK IMKONIYATLARI. *Science and innovation*, 3(Special Issue 18), 65-67.
4. Tulenova, K., Rasulev, E., & Mamadjonova, M. (2023). Value Dimension in a Technogenic Society. *Telematique*, 22(01), 2666-2670.
5. Шамшетова, Д. С. (2023). ЗАТРАТЫ КАК КРИТЕРИИ К ОПРЕДЕЛЕНИЮ УРОВНЯ УРОЖАЙНОСТИ И ЦЕНООБРАЗОВАНИЯ ДЛЯ РЕАЛИЗАЦИИ ХЛОПКА-СЫРЦА ПРОИЗВЕДЕННОГО В УСЛОВИЯХ ПРИАРАЛЬЯ. *Gospodarka i Innowacje*, 34, 319-324.
6. Shamshetova, D. S. (2019). Metody rascheta ekonomicheskogo ushcherba nanosimogo vreditelyami khlopchatnika za vegetatsionnyi period. *Ekonomika i predprinimatel'stvo*, 6, 855-858.
7. Utegenova, S., Muratbaeva, A., & Xaliqnazarova, G. (2021). PRACTICAL STATUS OF EXTERNAL QUALITY CONTROL OF AUDITS: ON THE EXAMPLE OF

UZBEKISTAN AND FOREIGN COUNTRIES. International journal of Business, Management and Accounting, 1(1).

8. Turdimuratovna, U. S. (2020). Methods of external quality control of audits. European Journal of Molecular & Clinical Medicine, 7(07), 2020.

9. Esbosinovna, T. G., & Ayzada, S. (2024). Sources Of Financing For Exports Of Agricultural Products. Periodica Journal of Modern Philosophy, Social Sciences and Humanities, 27, 66-68.

10. Reymova, T., & Tajenova, G. (2023). QISHLOQ XO 'JALIGI MAXSULOTLARI BILAN TA'MINLASHNING IQTISODIY MEKANIZMLARI. Central Asian Journal of Economics and Management, (1), 07-10.

11. Жамолова, Г. М. К., Хамрақулова, С. О. К., & Уралова, Н. Б. К. (2024). СОВЕРШЕНСТВОВАНИЕ НЕЙРОННЫХ СЕТЕЙ У ЧЕЛОВЕКА НА ПРИМЕРЕ РОБОТОТЕХНИКИ. Raqamli iqtisodiyot (Цифровая экономика), (6), 395-402.

12. Jamolova, G. (2023, May). PEDAGOGIK TAJRIBA SINOV ISHLARINI TASHKIL ETISH VA O 'TKAZISH METODIKASI. In International Scientific and Practical Conference on Algorithms and Current Problems of Programming.

13. Jamolova, G. M. (2022). PROFESSIONAL TA'LIM MUASSASALARIDA O 'QUVCHILARGA INFORMATIKA FANINI O 'QITISHNING METODIK MODEL. Educational Research in Universal Sciences, 1(2), 102-109.

14. Muzaffarovna, J. G. (2022). Investigation of a common emitter amplifier made in a bipolar transistor. Berlin Studies Transnational Journal of Science and Humanities, 2(1.5 Pedagogical sciences).

15. Jamolova, G. M. (2021). ELEKTRONIKA VA SXEMALAR FANINI RAQAMLI TEXNOLOGIYALAR ASOSIDA O'QITISH METODIKASI. Academic research in educational sciences, 2(5), 102-109.

16. Gile, D. (2009). Basic Concepts and Models for Interpreter and Translator Training. John Benjamins.

17. Angelelli, C. V. (2004). Medical Interpreting and Cross-cultural Communication. Cambridge University Press.

18. Stern, L. (2011). Training Interpreters. In K. Malmkjaer & K. Windle (Eds.), The Oxford Handbook of Translation Studies (pp. 490-509). Oxford University Press.